

The Dramatic Technique - Symbolism in Girish Karnad's Tughlaq

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Abstract

This paper is an attempt to study Girish Karnad's Tughlaq as a history play. Tughlaq is a play of many wonderful facts. A countless evidence of Karnad's dramatic achievement in Tughlaq is its immediate success and its secret lies in the techniques employed by playwright. It is immensely serious and also entertaining. It is the result of a magnificent effort of both intellectual energy and poetic imagination. It is full of pathos and sympathy. In order to produce such effects in the theatre Karnad, very skillfully employed various devices like spectacle, quick shift of scenes, quick shift of scenes, blackout, poetic elements, disguise, irony and symbolism.

Keywords: Tughlaq, Sympathy, Imagination, Techniques, Pathos, Symbolism.

Karnad has designed special costumes for Muhammad Tughlaq and other characters, keeping in view that they belong to the 14th century India and Muhammad was the Sultan, and also a great scholar. The 'visual aspects of production' on the stage are remarkably effective, and natural. He has used another technique of poetic sensibility. He endows the protagonist with rich poetic imagination. Muhammad, so often, becomes lyrical in his speeches in order to be convincing, fair, just and thereby he tries to win sympathy and support of his people so that they should 'understand' his visionary plans. Muhammad at times uses his poetic quality to move the audience emotionally, to exploit their sentiments. When he is deeply anguished and frustrated to think of his failures that he couldn't translate his dreams and ideals into reality Muhammad displays his poetic sensibility. His pathetic words:

I wanted to make for myself an image of Sadi's poems. I wanted every rose in it to be a poem.

Karnad's use of various symbols in Tughlaq is a part of dramatic technique through which he tries to explore the "inner landscape of the dramatic persona." In this context, Aziz and Aazam, Chess, Python and The prayer are striking symbols. These two characters symbolize those who are opportunists and men without any principle. Under disguise they cheat and deceive the eyes of others including the Sultan and

take undue advantages of the liberal, democratic and secular policies of Muhammad. Interestingly enough, the playwright achieves his satiric purpose through them. Through Aziz Karnad aims at justifying the statement that politics is the last refuge of scoundrels. Aziz takes delight in harming others and misappropriating huge public funds for his selfish ends. He symbolizes the class of such rogues and scoundrels even in present day politics.

The game of chess symbolizes the game of politics going on in the entire kingdom. Muhammad uses his brain in check-mating others in dealing with revolts and enemies as he does on the chess-board. He plays chess to solve intricate political problems and moves. 'Through chess, Karnad has highlighted Muhammad's manipulative skills in dealing with his adversaries.

He plays them as political pawns to gain his ends". The word python is used by the Old Man in Scene Eight for a long passage within the Daultabad fort. When he is asked about it by the young man the old man says, "yes, it's a long passage, a big passage, coiled like an enormous hollow python inside the belly of the fort. And we shall be far, far happier when that python breaks out and swallows everything in sight- every man, woman, child, and beast". The old man uses the python symbol to suggest that the fort is no longer a safe place on account of the cruel, savage and tyrannical behavior of the Sultan. The atmosphere within and without the fort had become hellish and chaotic where people had to die for no fault of their own, but due to starvation, want of medical aid. The economy of the country had gone to dogs due to bad policies of Sultan. Food riots had shaken the foundation of the fort as it is reported towards the end of the play. The old man also symbolically suggests destructive attitude of the Sultan who had become a savage, a tyrant and hence there was a danger for every man, woman, and child of being swallowed by the python. What a degeneration of Muhammad's personality!

Prayer is used as a symbol to reveal the 'real' Muhammad, altogether different from the 'ideal' one. The playwright deliberately creates an ironical situation at the time of prayer when Muhammad Tughlaq faces violent attack of his rebellions. Although he could avoid the aim, he must have been reminded of what he himself had done at the time of prayer killed his father and brother, as it was the talk of the town. Prayer is the time when one is always unarmed. It's a holy time. It must not be vitiated. If one does it he is a sinner. Muhammad forbids prayer in his kingdom when he realizes, though too late, that "prayers too are ridden with disease and must be exiled." This again is symbolic of hastening of Tughlaq's degeneration. With the 'exile' of prayer, something 'holy' within Tughlaq also is exiled. He is divorced from idealism, virtue and humanism. He becomes callous, cruel, revengeful and tyrant. He doesn't hesitate in getting his set-mother stoned to death as she had owned up to have Killed Nijib.

Vultures are the birds of prey symbolized by Tughlaq government officers, Amirs and the trusted ones who had turned hostile. His kingdom is now "honeycomb of diseases" and Muhammad can't leave "the patient in wilderness" unattended. His misery is that the birds are very close to him and every moment he expects a beak to dig into him and tear a muscle out. All his dreams, ideals and aspiration have ended in smoke and now he resembles a disillusioned romantic. The vultures thus symbolize his spiritual agony and anguish.

Thus Karnad has used symbols to make the play dramatic and forceful. His symbols have great emotional value. With symbols, the playwright has adorned his language and made his expression rich and effective. It is also one of the techniques employed in Tughlaq. In the light of the above, it can be said confidently that Karnad, with his dramatic skill and imagination, has made Tughlaq wonderful, fascinating and rich both in theme and technique.

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